

RESEARCH ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS MAGGI NOODLES

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the customer satisfaction on Nestle Maggi noodles. Customer satisfaction refers to the satisfaction that customer display in searching for purchasing, using, evaluating and disposing of products and services that they expect, will satisfied their need. Customer are highly complex individual subject to a variety of psychological and sociological needs apart from their survival needs. Needs and priorities of different customer segments differ drastically. This study analysis the brand preference of Nestle Maggi noodles by customer. The study evaluates the quality of Nestle Maggi noodles availed by customer, the media influences in consummation, the effect of the pricing policy in customer satisfaction. This study attempts to measure customer satisfaction as well as contributing to the commercial efficiency by the way suggestion to improve its probability in long term business. Quick food style is catching up fast because of more number of working couples, domestic fuel crisis, non-availability of reliable domestic servant and breaking up of joint family system. Neither time nor patience to prepare the ingredients and wholesome food in the house itself, the high price of ingredients and ready mix are also a significant factor responsible for the spectacular increase in the demand for Maggi noodles product. Nestle was a global processed food manufacturer having its headquarters in Switzerland. The Indian Subsidiary Nestle India, began its operation in 1912 with the growing economic liberalization in India it tried to establish its business. Firstly, it was dealing in agriculture and dairy sector. In 1980 it launched brand Maggi in 80's business environment, their priority was to position noodles as an Indian product. Therefore, they targeted the working women, Professionals living alone and children. They tried to communicate the positioning of brand Maggi as a tasty and healthy food, which was convenient to cook, consuming less time. The brand Maggi was targeted specifically according to various segmenting the east and south parts of India where rice was the major food item. They launched rice noodles to attract more customers in these areas. They added various segments such as dhal Atta, vegetable Atta and rice noodles. In traditional noodles it added variants like curry, masala, tomato, lemon masala and chilly chow as rice variants.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, Nestle Maggi noodles.

INTRODUCTION

Maggi instant noodles are popular in India and Malaysia. Nestle has 39% market share in Malaysia, where "Maggi" is synonymous with instant noodles, and had 90% market share in India prior to a nationwide ban by the Food Safety and Standards Authority of India. Following the ban, the market share was reduced to 53% in India. In Malaysia, fried noodles made from Maggi noodles are called Maggi goreng.

Nestle is among the largest consumer packaged goods companies in the world, founded and headquarter in Vevey, Switzerland. Nestle originated in a 1905 merger of the Anglo-Swiss milk company. Which was established in 1866 by brothers George page and Charies page, and the Farine lactee Henry Nestle company, which was founded in 1866 by Henry Nestle, Whose name ment "little nest". The company grew significantly during the first world war, and following the second world war, eventually expanding its offering beyond its early condensed milk and infant formula products. Today, the company operates in 86 countries around the world.

Maggi instant noodles, foods major Nestel's flagship brand that has dominated the Indian instant noodles market for nearly three decades, is losing market share on a monthly basis to newer entrants. Such as GlaxoSmithKline's(GSK) Horlicks Foodless, Unilever's Knorr Soupy noodles, Big bazar tasty treat, Top ramen and several other smaller players according to data by market research firm Nielsen.

Customer satisfaction refers to the satisfaction that consumer display in searching for purchasing, using, evaluating and disposing of products and services that they expect, will satisfied their need. Customer are highly complex individual subject to a variety of psychological and sociological needs apart from their survival needs. Needs and priorities of different consumer segments differ drastically. This study analysis the brand preference of Nestle Maggi noodles by customer. The study evaluates the quality of Nestle Maggi noodles availed by consumer, the media influences in consummation, the effect of the pricing policy in consumer satisfaction. This study attempts to measure customer satisfaction as well as contributing to the commercial efficiency by the way suggestion to improve its probability in long term business.

Quick food style is catching up fast because of more number of working couples, domestic fuel crisis, non-availability of reliable domestic servant and breaking up of joint family system. Neither time nor patience to prepare the ingredients and wholesome food in the house itself, the high price of ingredients and ready mix are also a significant factors responsible for the spectacular increase in the demand for Maggi noodles product.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer perception is a process by which a customer senses the surroundings, analysis the information and assigns meaning to it. The information retained defines the ways to meet his need and wants. Customer perception is relevant for marketers as customer base their

decision on perception rather than facts. All the marketing strategies revolve around creating a favourable perception of the product in the minds of the customers. Controversies surrounding food products and beverages are not new to India.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- 1.To study the brand preference of Nestle Maggi noodles by customer.
- 2.To evaluate the quality of nestle Maggi noodles availed by customer
- 3.To analyze out the media influences on consumption.
- 4.To evaluate the effect of the pricing policy on customer satisfaction.
- 5.To identify the reasons for purchasing various brands by consumers.

Hypotheses done for the Maggi noodles

Quick food style are catching up fast because more number of working couples, domestic fuels crisis, non availability of reliable domestic servants and breaking up of joint family system. Neither time nor patience to prepare the ingredients and wholesome food in the house itself, the high price of ingredients and ready mix are also a significant factor responsible for the spectacular increase in the demand fo Maggi noodles product.

- 1.There is no significant relationship between the impact of media and purchase decision.
- 2.There is no significant difference between influencers and purchase decision.
3. There is no significant relationship between preference for more new varities and purchase decision .
4. There is no significant difference between quality of noodles and purchase decision.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research design

The research design is the conceptual structure within which research is conducted; It constitute the blueprint for the collection, Measurement and analysis of data. Since the research problem is well defined and attempt is made to describe the existing phenomena relating to the measurement of brand equity, this research fits well in to the empirical research design.

Sampling design:

Nature of sample

Customers of Nestle Maggi noodles are the source of data collection for the study.

Area of study

The study is conducted in social medias.

Sample size

The total number of samples are 180 were taken in to account.

Method of data collection

Primary source

Standardized questionnaire used as primary source for the purpose of study. It The questionnaire has both open ended and close ended questions.

Secondary source

The following are the source for the study.

- Various research generals and periodicals.
- Various website on internet.

FINDINGS:

- There are 93.1% people who are aware about nestle Maggi noodles.
- 73.9% of People became aware of the Maggi noodles through advertisement. 13.7% became aware of Maggi noodles from friends and 8.6% became aware of it from the family members.
- Around 53.7% of people are effected more by advertising the Maggi properly.
- The consumption of Maggi noodles done by the people are sometimes more than 47.4%.
- Among all 50.3% people are preferred by the advertisement and hence started liking the product.
- The Maggi which contains a nutrition in it is around 52% and are partially agreed by the customers.
- Suggested by Maggi introduced a new favorable at 68% of people.
- Maggi noodles are preferred by the children more response at 50.3%
- Maggi noodles created a good brand name is 98% of people agreed.

CONCLUSION:

In the modern world, customer taste and preferences are changing day by day because of rapid changing technology in the food production. A satisfied customer will soon change to other product but a loyal customer will not be so. The success of manufacturing depends on creation of new customer and retaining the existing customer. Several factors are influencing the customers while they purchase a particular product. Hence manufacturers should identify the target group and provide product to satisfy all type of customers. The Maggi noodles has been able to differentiate itself from other noodles; Maggi being taken has generic to noodles is hampering other extant product category. Competitors have high grounds to capture the differentiating than from being Maggi. It makes others possible product category indianized brand of products, and has Indian being more aware of their culture and large segment being typical and conservative about their culture, there are *more* chance that manufacture would be successful if it creates a brand close to Indian culture in wording to positioning. Has India is growing; old Indian brands are also regaining momentum worldwide; manufacturer could catch the trend of market.

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